

1 **Multicomponent Network Formation in Selective**
2 **Layer of Composite Membrane for CO₂ Separation**

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8 **Supporting Information for the Manuscript**

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Figure S4. DMT-modulus scans of three spots on P1500 membranes: (a) Pristine membrane without additives; (b-f) Membranes with additives: (b) JED600PPG380; (c) JED600PPG640; (d) JED600TPT302; (e) JT403PPG640; (f) JT403TPT302.

12 **Figure S5.** Histograms of the DMT-modulus scans of three spots on P1500 membranes: (a) Pristine
 13 membrane without additives; (b-f) Membrane with additives: (b) JED600PPG380; (c) JED600PPG640;
 14 (d) JED600TPT302; (e) JT403PPG640; (f) JT403TPT302. The black circle marks the frequency value
 15 used for normalization.

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Figure S6. AFM height scans of three spots on P1500 membranes: (a) Pristine membrane without additives; (b-f) Membranes with additives: (b) JED600PPG380; (c) JED600PPG640; (d) JED600TPT302; (e) JT403PPG640; (f) JT403TPT302.

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Table S4. Parameters of the stiffer phase's lateral size (domain size by FWHM method) and proportion to softer phase (histogram peak-ratio), averaged over the DMT images of three scans.

	Pristine	JED600 PPG380	JED600 PPG640	JED600 TPT302	JT403 PPG640	JT403 TPT302
Domain size (μm)	0.23 ± 0.21	0.26 ± 0.27	0.15 ± 0.13	0.11 ± 0.07	0.49 ± 0.48	0.3 ± 0.24
Histogram peak-ratio	3.4 ± 1.3	3.1 ± 1.3	1.2 ± 0.4	0.9 ± 0.2	9.9 ± 3.5	2.9 ± 0.8

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